

A17 Complex nutritional management of a KWPN horse with multiple pathologies

César López Císcar^{1,2*}, Alba Ibáñez López^{1,2}, José Luis López Rivero² and Patricia Harris³

¹Servicio de Nutrición Clínica Equina, Clínica Equina Equisouls, Valencia, España, ²Departamento de Anatomía y Anatomía Patológica Comparadas y Toxicología, Universidad de Córdoba, Córdoba, España, ³Equine Studies Group, Waltham Petcare Science Institute, Waltham-on-the-Wolds, UK
E-mail: z32locic@uco.es

Introduction: Nutrition can be part of the problem, the cause, the consequence, and/or the solution to numerous pathologies in horses. Therefore, it is essential to formulate diets based on a complete clinical history and evaluation. Close monitoring enables relevant adaptations to be made¹. This report outlines the nutritional management of a horse admitted to Equisouls Equine Clinic with multiple initial clinical issues and which went on to develop additional complications over the following months; the various clinical issues included severe weight loss, sabulous cystitis, gastric ulcers, severe dental disease, and small colon impaction.

Animals, material and methods: The patient was a 553 kg, 18-year-old KWPN gelding used for dressage lessons. It presented with a BCS of 2/9, severe muscle atrophy, and poor dental health. Very limited clinical history data from the previous three years was available. A detailed dietary assessment and re-formulation were conducted, and follow-up care was provided at home. Monitoring of the horse and regular communication with the owner was instigated.

Results and discussion: The horse's diet on admission consisted of ad libitum wheat straw (1.54% BW as DM) and a mixture of different cereals (73:27 forage:concentrate ratio) without additional vitamins or minerals giving a total DM intake of 2% BW. Deficiencies in intakes of DE (38%), crude protein (20%), as well as lysine, threonine, Ca, P, Na, Cl, Mg, S, Cu, I, Mn, Zn, Se, vitamin A, E, B1, and B2 were noted; sugar and starch intakes were 2.44 g/kg BW/day and 1.22 g/kg BW/meal. An initial balanced energy/protein rich diet was recommended, but the equestrian centre was not able to comply with it and the horse had to be moved multiple times in search of a suitable facility. To facilitate management of the ongoing pathologies as well as those that subsequently developed, variations in the core diet and medical treatment were proposed. Unfortunately, the case was complicated by the owner's financial limitations and the lack of caregivers' collaboration. As a result, many nutritional and medical recommendations could not be implemented in a timely manner—or at all. An effect of the necessary measures not being taken when needed, was that the preexisting clinical conditions contributed to the development of new pathologies, further complicating recovery. Overall, the patient received flunixin (1.1 mg/kg/24 h IV for 5 days), trimethoprim-sulfadiazine (30 mg/kg/12 h PO for 5 days), omeprazole (4 mg/kg/24 h PO for 21 days), bladder lavage, and crown odontoplasty. The final balanced diet consisted of 14 kg of grass hay, 80 g of salt, 400 g of sunflower oil, 0.5 kg of a low non-structural carbohydrate complementary feed and 110 g of a balancer per day. It took one year to implement all recommended measures and for the patient to achieve a BCS of 5/9 and a BW of 650 kg.

Conclusion: This report highlights the importance of an integrative nutritional approach, alongside timely medical treatment, in managing a patient with multiple coexisting pathologies. Furthermore, it underscores the detrimental impact of inadequate diet and management on equine health and emphasizes that delays in implementing appropriate programmes can lead to the emergence of new, preventable clinical conditions.

References:

[1] Harris, et al. (2022) UK-Vet Equine. 6:50.